

unfavourable negative contribution of entropy may arise due to the restriction of degrees of freedom of solvent molecules in the vicinity of the metal ion and this effect is very much pronounced with metal ions of high charge¹⁰ and nature of the ligand. The log *K* values reported here are accurate to ± 0.3 log units and the values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS are reliable to ± 0.04 kcal mol⁻¹, ± 0.5 kcal mol⁻¹ and 2 cal K⁻¹ mol⁻¹ respectively.

The order of stability of trivalent metal complexes follows the sequence, Pr^{III} > Nd^{III} < Sm^{III} > Gd^{III}. Such difference in the trend of stability constants is not uncommon in the case of lanthanides¹¹ and this may be traced to be due to varying degree of stabilisations arising out of interaction of 4*f* metal orbitals with ligand field¹².

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Polarographic Studies on Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cadmium(II) with some Amino Acids as Primary Ligands and 2,2'-Bipyridyl as Secondary Ligand

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INERACTION of cadmium(II) with amino acids and 2,2'-bipyridyl (BP) has been investigated polarographically by many workers¹. The ternary systems of Cd^{II} with BP as primary ligand and

amino acids as secondary ligands have also been studied by pH-titration method². As no polarographic studies on ternary complexes of Cd^{II} with glycine (GL), DL- α -alanine (AL) and DL-valine (VL) as primary ligands and BP as secondary ligand have so far been made, we report the results herein.

Experimental

Stock solutions of the ligands glycine (B.D.H.), DL- α -alanine (B.D.H.), DL-valine (SD's) and 2,2'-bipyridyl (AnalaR) were prepared in double-distilled water. Stock solution of CdCl₂·6H₂O (SISCO) was prepared in nitric acid to prevent hydrolysis and its metal content was determined by titration with EDTA³. 'Mercury for polarography' (E. Merck) was used for the DME.

Polarographic measurements were performed with 5×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ Cd^{II} and 0.001% Triton X-100 at *I* = 0.5 mol dm⁻³ (KNO₃) and at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Purified nitrogen gas was passed through the solutions to remove dissolved oxygen.

Polarograms were recorded on a Toshniwal CLO2B digital polarograph. The DME had *t* = 4 s (open-circuit) at *h*₀₁₁ = 49 cm (35.25 cm in case of Cd^{II}-BP system). All potentials refer to SCE. pH measurements were made on a ELICO LI-120 digital pH-meter equipped with glass and calomel electrodes.

The protonation constants of amino acids were determined by Irving and Rossotti method⁴.

Results and Discussion

Dissociation constants (Table 1) of ligands were calculated from the pH-titration data using Rossotti and Rossotti's method⁵. For BP, the values given are taken from literature⁶.

TABLE 1—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF LIGANDS
I = 0.5 mol dm⁻³ (KNO₃), Temp. = 35°

Ligand	p <i>K</i> ₁	p <i>K</i> ₂
Glycine ^a	9.55	
DL- α -Alanine ^a	9.70	
DL-Valine ^a	9.51	
2,2'-Bipyridyl ^b	4.40	2.80

^aPresent work. ^bRef. 6.

Binary systems: The studies of binary and ternary systems were made under identical conditions⁷.

The reduction of Cd^{II} gave a single, reversible and diffusion-controlled wave in absence and presence of ligands. An increase in ligand concentration or pH shifted the half-wave potential of Cd^{II} to more negative values indicating the complex formation between the metal ion and the ligand.

In case of amino acids as ligand, pH was adjusted with KOH. The total concentration of amino

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acids was varied in the range $(0.83-4.00) \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³. The complexes of Cd^{II} with amino acids were studied in the pH range 7.0-10.5. The complexes with BP were studied pH range 3-6 and the pH was adjusted with HNO₃. The concentration of free ligand was calculated from the pH and the total amount present using appropriate pK values.

Plots of $\Delta E_{1/2}$ vs log X for Cd^{II}-amino acid and -BP systems were not linear, thereby indicating the stepwise complexation. The experimental data were processed by the method of DeFord and Hume⁸.

All the three amino acids and BP formed three complexes i.e. Cd(L)⁺, Cd(L)₂, Cd(L)₃⁻ and Cd(BP)₂²⁺, Cd(BP)₃³⁺, Cd(BP)₃³⁺. The overall stability constants are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—OVERALL STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR BINARY COMPLEXES OF CADMIUM(II)

I=0.5 mol dm ⁻³ (KNO ₃), Temp.=35°			
System	log β ₁	log β ₂	log β ₃
CdII-GL	4.45	6.96	9.39
CdII-AL	4.18	6.72	9.06
CdII-VL	3.65	6.01	8.06
CdII-BP	4.60	7.30	9.83

Ternary systems: The mixed-ligand systems were studied by keeping the concentration of amino acid constant while varying that of BP (pH 8.5-9.5). The concentration of BP was varied in the range $(0.5-6.0) \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³. On increasing the concentration of BP, the half-wave potentials shifted towards more negative values. The shifts were always greater than those observed for single ligand systems. Schaap and McMasters method⁹ was used to determine the overall stability constants of the mixed complexes.

The equation used at constant ionic-strength is

$$F_{00}(L, BP) = \text{antilog} \left(\frac{0.4343 nF}{RT} \Delta E_{1/2} + \log \frac{I_2}{I_1} \right) = A + B[BP] + C[BP]^2 \quad (1)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} A &= 1 + \beta_{01}[L^-] + \beta_{02}[L^-]^2 + \beta_{03}[L^-]^3 \\ B &= \beta_{10} + \beta_{11}[L^-] + \beta_{12}[L^-]^2 \\ C &= \beta_{20} + \beta_{21}[L^-] \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

and β_{0n} and β_{m0} are the binary stability constants of the simple metal complexes with amino acids and bipyridyl, respectively; β₁₁, β₁₂ and β₂₁ are the overall stability constants for the formation of the ternary complexes, Cd(L)(BP)⁺, Cd(L)₂(BP) and Cd(L)(BP)₂²⁺, respectively. The values of overall stability constants for the ternary systems are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—OVERALL STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR TERNARY COMPLEXES OF CADMIUM(II)

I=0.5 mol dm ⁻³ (KNO ₃), Temp.=35°			
System	log β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁
CdII-GL-BP	8.15	10.53	10.17
CdII-AL-BP	7.18	10.05	10.14
CdII-VL-BP	6.98	9.21	9.33

The stability of mixed-ligand complexes can be compared with that of simple complexes. The equilibrium constant for the reaction,

is given by the relation,

$$\Delta \log K = \log \beta_{11} - (\log \beta_{01} + \log \beta_{10}) \quad (3)$$

The statistical value of $\Delta \log K$ for coordination of two different bidentate ligands for an octahedral coordination sphere is $-0.4 \log \text{units}^{10}$ (for other situations, the statistical values of $\Delta \log K$'s may be less but are always negative). The respective calculated values of $\Delta \log K$ for ternary systems, for example for 1:1:1 Cd^{II}-L-BP complexes, are -0.90 , -0.97 and -1.27 . These higher negative values suggest that the mixed species are less stable than the simple 1:1 complexes, or in other words, BP binds better to Cd^{II} than to the binary Cd(L)⁺ complexes. This is due to the fact that more coordination positions are available on Cd^{II} than on ML complexes.

Relative stability of a mixed complex with respect to the parent binary complexes can also be evaluated from the expression,

where, $m+n=p$.

The mixing constant (K_m) is given by¹¹

$$\begin{aligned} K_m &= [Cd(L)_m(BP)_n] / [Cd(L)_p]^{m/p} [Cd(BP)_p]^{n/p} \\ &= \beta_{mn} / \beta_{0p}^{m/p} \beta_{p0}^{n/p} \end{aligned}$$

or $\log K_m = \log \beta_{mn} - 1/p(m \log \beta_{0p} + n \log \beta_{p0})$

The stabilisation constant (K_s) for ligands of equal denticity is given by

$$\log K_s = \log K_m - \log \frac{p!}{m!n!}$$

Calculated values of $\log K_m$ and $\log K_s$ for 1:1:1, 1:2:1 and 1:1:2 complexes are listed in Table 4 for the ternary systems. The positive values of mixing constants and stabilisation constants show that the mixed complexes are relatively more stable than the simple binary complexes. The stability order of 1:1:1 ternary complexes with respect to the primary ligand (amino acid), was found to be glycine > alanine > valine.

TABLE 4—VALUES OF $\Delta \log K$, $\log K_m$ AND $\log K_s$ FOR Cd^{II}-L-BP SYSTEMS

I=0.5 mol dm ⁻³ (KNO ₃), Temp.=35°						
Primary ligand (L)	m	n	p	$\Delta \log K$	$\log K_m$	$\log K_s$
GL	1	1	2	-0.90	1.02	0.72
	2	1	3	-1.03	0.99	0.51
	1	2	3	-1.58	0.49	0.01
AL	1	1	2	-0.97	0.80	0.50
	2	1	3	-1.27	0.73	0.26
	1	2	3	-1.34	0.57	0.09
VL	1	1	2	-1.27	0.32	0.02
	2	1	3	-1.40	0.56	0.08
	1	2	3	-1.62	0.09	-0.39

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Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Diphenyl Sulphoxide by Chloramine-B in Aqueous Acid Medium

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THE oxidation kinetics of diphenyl sulphoxide with chloramine-B have been studied in aqueous acetic acid medium. The reaction involves an initial slow step followed by a rapid one, indicating that the reaction follows complicated kinetics.

Experimental

Diphenyl sulphoxide was prepared by the Friedel-Crafts reaction of benzene with thionyl chloride¹. Chloramine-B (CAB) (sodium *N*-chlorobenzenesulphonamide) was prepared by partial chlorination of benzenesulphonamide². Sodium

sulphate was employed to maintain the ionic strength.

The kinetic studies were carried out in 50% (v/v) aqueous acetic acid at an ionic strength of 0.23 mol dm⁻³ under pseudo-first order conditions (at 35±0.5°). The reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted CAB iodometrically.

The stoichiometry (1 : 1) of the oxidation was determined with varying amounts of oxidant in excess over the substrate. The products were detected by tlc.

Results and Discussion

The order with respect to oxidant (1.7) was found out by half-life method³. For all the runs, rates were determined when 40% of the reaction was over and from that rate constant was calculated. The fairly constant *k* values confirm the fractional order with respect to oxidant (Table 1). The rate of the reaction was independent of [sulphoxide]. The *k* values are fairly constant within the limits of experimental error (Table 1). The rate increased with increase in [Acid] and the plot of log *k* vs log [H⁺] was linear with a gradient 1.82 (*r*, 0.997).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF REACTANTS CONCENTRATION ON RATE OF OXIDATION OF DIPHENYL SULPHOXIDE BY CHLORAMINE-B (CAB)

Medium : Aqueous acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v), [H⁺]=0.95 mol dm⁻³, Temp.=308 K

[Sulphoxide] ₀ × 10 ² mol dm ⁻³	[CAB] ₀ × 10 ² mol dm ⁻³	<i>k</i> × 10 ² s	AcOH* %	<i>k</i> × 10 ² s
3.44	0.93	6.8	50	6.9
3.44	1.63	6.9	55	7.6
3.44	1.85	6.2	60	9.7
3.44	2.32	6.6	65	13.5
3.44	2.78	6.2	10μ ^a	
			(mol dm ⁻²)	
3.44	3.70	6.7		
1.98	1.63	6.4	1.2	8.5
2.75	1.63	6.3	2.3	6.3
4.13	1.63	6.5	3.5	5.9
5.50	1.63	7.2	4.7	5.1
6.88	1.63	6.8		

^a[CAB]₀ = 1.63 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³; [Sulphoxide]₀ = 3.44 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³.

The rate increased with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium (Table 1). The plot of log *k* vs 1/*D* was linear with a positive slope, indicating positive ion-dipole interactions. Addition of one of the reaction products benzenesulphonamide (BSA) had no effect on the rate (Table 1). The rates decreased with the increase in ionic strength of the medium (Table 1). Addition of Cl⁻ increased the rate very sharply. The reaction was too fast and it could not be followed.

The reaction was studied at four different temperatures 35, 40, 42.5 and 45°. The values of